

Driving without Driver in Public Transportation

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Abstract

In the emerging model of public transportation with fully automated mini-busses, the suppression of the driver and the introduction of external intervention teams, raised questions on by whom and how all the formal and informal services of the driver can be still offered, preserving the current high level quality of service. In this paper, we present our experience from the AVENUE project in the deployment of IT based services targeting in offering the driver assistance services in a driverless public transportation mini-bus, discussing the related issues, in their implementation. A novel artificial intelligence (AI) supported framework that enables wide adoption of these services is also presented envisioning significant enhancement of safety and security levels in autonomous public transportation as well as passengers trust. The AVENUE ecosystem and the associated services are expected to provide the pillars for wide adoption and passengers' engagement of future fully automated public transportation mobility.

Keywords: *Public transportation, driverless operation, services, artificial intelligence*

Στο αναδυόμενο μοντέλο των δημόσιων μεταφορών με τα πλήρως αυτόνομα μίνι λεωφορεία, η κατάργηση του οδηγού και η εισαγωγή εξωτερικών ομάδων παρέμβασης, έθεσε ερωτήματα σχετικά με το από ποιον και πώς μπορούν να εξακολουθούν να προσφέρονται όλες οι τυπικές και άτυπες υπηρεσίες του οδηγού, διατηρώντας το σημερινό υψηλό επίπεδο ποιότητας των υπηρεσιών. Σε αυτή την ανακοίνωση, παρουσιάζουμε την εμπειρία μας από το έργο AVENUE στην ανάπτυξη υπηρεσιών βασισμένων στην ΤΠ που στοχεύουν στην προσφορά υπηρεσιών υποστήριξης σε ένα μίνι λεωφορείο δημόσιας μεταφοράς χωρίς οδηγό, συζητώντας τα σχετικά ζητήματα κατά την εφαρμογή τους. Παρουσιάζεται επίσης ένα νέο πλαίσιο υποστηριζόμενο από τεχνητή νοημοσύνη (TN) που επιτρέπει την ευρεία υιοθέτηση αυτών των υπηρεσιών, το οποίο οραματίζεται σημαντική βελτίωση των επιπέδων ασφάλειας και προστασίας στις αυτόνομες δημόσιες μεταφορές, καθώς και της εμπιστοσύνης των επιβατών. Το οικοσύστημα AVENUE και οι σχετικές υπηρεσίες αναμένεται να αποτελέσουν τους πυλώνες για την ευρεία υιοθέτηση και αποδοχή των μελλοντικών πλήρως αυτοματοποιημένων δημόσιων μεταφορών.

Λέξεις-κλειδιά: *Δημόσιες μεταφορές, λειτουργία χωρίς οδηγό, υπηρεσίες, τεχνητή νοημοσύνη*

1. Introduction

Autonomous or Fully Automated mini-buses (AVs) offer a new model for the future public transportation (Iclodean et al. 2020), allowing personalized transportation, adapted to all passengers, while enabling a true autonomous mobility as a service (Maas) concept (Bosch et al. 2018), (Cruz & Sarmento 2020). The target of the current technological developments of the different manufacturers is to achieve a driver free operation. However, the implications of suppressing the driver are not yet clearly understood by the operators and passengers (Chehria et al. 2019). Drivers in public transportation, not only assure the driving of the bus, but also provide a series of formal and informal services to the passengers and the vehicle, ranging from controlling the status of the vehicle, to assisting the passengers, and ensuring a level of security and safety.

On the other hand, numerous concerns of the end users can be recognized regarding the safety and robustness of the AVs that directly affect the final user acceptance of the new technology, (Nunes et al. 2018), (Lee et al. 2020). The prospective passengers fear several possible occasions that could occur in case there is no driver in the bus (Claybrook & Kildare 2018). Indicatively, no person will be in the bus to perform first aid if required, while there is a feeling of discomfort being all alone in the bus at night, especially in certain neighborhoods. Furthermore, there is no authority figure present to keep passengers calm (e.g., school kids), whereas incidents of vandalism, bag snatching, indoor fighting, potentially dangerous unaccompanied luggage may arise. More vulnerable people, kids or elderly, as well as people with special needs, may require dedicated help to get on or off the bus, while their relatives may be anxious about whether they are safe if no driver is present. Moreover, lost or forgotten items, will be left into the vehicle since there is no one to collect them, whereas they impose a serious security risk if malicious intentions are associated with them.

With the suppression of the driver and the introduction of external intervention teams, the question is raised by whom and how all the formal and informal services of the driver can be still offered, preserving the current high level quality of service. In the frame of the H2020 EU project AVENUE, targeting the deployment of on-demand, door-to-door public transportation services with fully automated mini-buses, we have developed and experimenting with different IT based solutions and services that will provide to the passengers similar services as if the driver was on-board. For this a novel artificial intelligence (AI) supported framework has been developed that enables wide adoption of these services and being very promising in providing a significant enhancement of safety and security levels in autonomous public transportation as well as passengers trust. In this work, the diverse characteristics of the AVENUE holistic services along with the associated framework are introduced. Furthermore, COVID-19 pandemic implications to the deployment of these services are discussed and novel adopted solutions are thoroughly presented as integral part that formulate the new virus-proof era of mobility. Section 2 presents the AVENUE ecosystem, along with the vehicles and the service operation overview. Section 3 thoroughly describes the passenger services, i.e. safety and assistance services that aim to facilitate the passengers to engage the new mobility paradigm that will be formulated. Finally, section 4, provides the deployment planning of the services into the AVENUE ecosystem and beyond.

2. AVENUE Ecosystem

2.1 Overview of the AVENUE Project

AVENUE aims to design and carry out full-scale demonstrations of urban transport automation by deploying, for the first time worldwide, fleets of autonomous minibuses in low to medium demand areas in 4 European demonstrator cities (Geneva, Lyon, Copenhagen and Luxembourg) and 2 replicator sites (Sion, Esch-sur-Alzette). The AVENUE vision for future public transport in urban and suburban areas is that autonomous vehicles will ensure safe, rapid, economic, sustainable and personalised transport of passengers. AVENUE introduces disruptive public transportation paradigms on the basis of on-demand, door-to-door services, aiming to set up a new model of public transportation, by revisiting the offered public transportation services, and aiming to suppress prescheduled fixed bus itineraries.

At the end of the AVENUE project the mission is to have demonstrated that autonomous vehicles will become the future solution for public transport. The AVENUE project will demonstrate the economic, environmental and social potential of autonomous vehicles for both companies and public commuters while assessing the vehicle road behaviour safety.

Vehicle and transport services that substantially enhance the passenger experience as well as the overall quality and value of the transport service are designed and tested, adapted also for passengers with special needs, like elderly people, people with disabilities and vulnerable users. Road behaviour, security of the autonomous vehicles and passengers' safety are central points of the AVENUE project.

The target of the AVENUE project is to develop an integrated system comprising of automated vehicles and services that independently select and optimize the vehicle destination and routes, based on passenger demands, creating thus what we call an "autonomous vehicles public transportation service". In relation to the SAE levels (SAE International 2018), the AVENUE project will operate SAE Level 4 vehicles, that is, operating in a predefined mapped area (which is always the case for public transportation services), and with vehicles that do not have driving wheel and pedals, and which are receiving destination instructions from a remote system (what we call the "fleet orchestration" (Bestmile 2020)).

2.2 The AVENUE Autonomous Vehicles

In AVENUE we are using the NAVYA Autonom Shuttle (NAVYA 2020), which has a capacity of 14 persons, and is authorised, in the AVENUE sites, to operate at a maximum speed of up to 25-30 km/h in an open street (although technically can achieve speeds of more than 60Km/h).

The vehicles are capable to recognise obstacles (and identify some of them), identify moving and stationary objects, and autonomously decide to bypass them or wait behind them, based on the defined policies. For example with small changes in its route the AVENUE shuttle is able to bypass a parked car, while it will slow down and follow behind a slowly moving car. The AVENUE vehicles are able to handle different complex road situations, like entering and

exiting round-about in the presence of other fast running cars, stop in zebra crossings, and communicate with infrastructure via V2I interfaces (e.g. red light control).

The AVENUE vehicles operate with an obligatory safety operator present in the vehicle. However in the best site, in Geneva, Belle-Idee (TPG 2021), the safety operator is simply present and the vehicle operates more than 99% of the time without any operator intervention. The target is to reach almost 100% operation without operator intervention.

2.3 Autonomous Vehicle Service Operation Overview

We distinguish in AVENUE three levels of control: *micro-navigation*, *macro-navigation* and *fleet orchestration*. **Micro-navigation** is fully integrated in the vehicle and implements the road behaviour of the vehicle; micro-navigation will provide the required obstacle recognition and bypassing, lane changing (when authorised), turning points, speed control etc.

The next level of control is the **macro-navigation** where the destination is defined and the path to follow. This is the same function as the widely used GPS navigators that provide to the driver of the individual vehicle instructions of the road to take, but are not interfering to the on-road driver decisions.

In the operation of a public transportation service we will have a large number of vehicles operating within the designated service area. Which vehicle will serve which trip request is done by the **fleet orchestration** system, which manages (among others) the choice of the specific vehicle that will be used in reply to a specific passenger trip request, based on the transport policies defined by the operators. The complete planning is dynamically adapted depending on new trip requests, changing street/weather conditions, changes in the vehicle status and operator policies to respect.

3. Passenger services

In traditional, driver based, public transportation, a driver is always present in the bus. Although the common idea for the driver is that he “drives the vehicle”, in reality a driver provides numerous services, formal or informal, for the passengers and the care of the vehicle. Passengers can ask questions to the driver about itineraries, ticketing issues and even asked to be informed, for example, to go out at a specific stop (especially for persons with special needs). The driver will also help wheel chair passengers to enter the vehicle, guide elderly and visually impaired for a safe trip, and of course intervene in case of an accident, incivilities in the bus or vandalism, providing thus a sense of safety to the passengers. The driver also controls the status of the vehicle, and decides to bring it for maintenance or cleaning, in coordination with the operator services.

All these services provided by the driver contribute in the service quality of the public transportation, improving the safety, wellbeing and passenger satisfaction. The suppression of the driver in an autonomous public transportation service, and the need to maintain the same level of transport service quality, means that new innovative services must be introduced, using either electronic means or by encouraging social mutual assistance, when possible.

In-vehicle security

Figure 1: *Dashboard of the in-vehicle AVENUE security and safety services: AI supported video and audio analytics are available, along with a variety of real-time measurements and assessments of the environment, accompanied with appropriate notifications*

However the introduction of new services might have important implications for the vehicle design and required new infrastructure that needs to be installed by the public transport service operator. Furthermore, due to the novelty of the driverless operation of public transportation buses, one should not underestimate the psychological effects that an autonomous vehicle can have to parts of the population. For example, what will be the reaction of an elderly person that is used to a fixed itinerary, when the shuttle will, each time, change its itinerary based on the trip requests of the moment? It might generate anxiety (am I in the wrong bus?) or even fear, reducing the acceptance of the service, since there is no driver to provide an explanation and reassure the passenger (we clearly understand however that this issue is transient problem, which will disappear when the current young generations that will grow up with this type of services will reach an advanced age). In addition the automatization of the surveillance of the passengers (for identification of aggressions, vandalism etc) raises many questions regarding privacy and data protection, that needs to be addressed and regulated before the services can be deployed, so that they will be acceptable by the citizens.

3.1 Safety Services

A critical aspect of the envisioned autonomous public transportation system is related to the safety of the passenger, since a new reality is formed as a result of the absence of the bus driver and the increased threat from terrorism in European cities. Typically, drivers are trained to handle incidents of passengers' abnormal behaviour, incidents of petty crimes, etc. according to standard procedures adopted by the transport operator. Several concerns of the end users regarding the safety and robustness of the AVs can be identified. Among them, no

Figure 2: People fighting within the autonomous shuttle: The petty crime detection and notification subsystem is activated and provides abnormal activity detection and notification

person will be in the bus to perform first aid if required, while there is an atmosphere of anxiety being all alone in the bus at night-time, especially in particular districts. In addition, there is no authority figure on-board to keep passengers calm (e.g., school kids), while incidents of vandalism, bag snatching, indoor fighting, potentially dangerous unaccompanied luggage may occur.

To address the aforementioned concerns on social and personal safety and security into the vehicle, certain measures need to be implemented. Surveillance using sensors such as cameras and microphones, as well as smart software and hardware in the bus are deemed essential to maximize the feeling of security and the actual level of security. Moreover, implementing a solution for enhancing the safety and security inside the autonomous buses will support safekeeping not only the users of the autonomous public bus but also the vehicle itself. In this context, a safety service entitled “Enhance the sense of security and trust”, has been designed and implemented, introducing a novel video and audio analytics software module based on an AI framework. This approach enables the employment of an embedded security subsystem or cloud-based services according to the public transport operator needs.

The service addresses the timely, accurate, robust and automatic detection of various petty crime types or misdemeanors as well as the assistance of authorized end-users towards the re-identification of any offenders. The petty crimes that are targeted for identification by the sensors include: petty theft like bag snatching and pickpocketing, vandalism, aggression, illegal consumption of cigarettes, public intoxication, simple assault and disorderly conduct. For example the detection of a petty crime may raise a notification or an alert to the supervisor and/or the suitable authorities. This may be followed by appropriate notifications and/or instructions to the passengers, while the vehicle may implement respective actions.

Figure 3: Vandalism actions within an autonomous shuttle: Graffiti painting and window attack are detected by the petty crime detection and notification subsystem and activate mitigation protocol

The service is provided through a dashboard, as depicted in Figure 1, so that to facilitate the complete monitoring of the in-vehicle premises, through video feeds and audio spectrograms, but also useful information, such as event history, environmental conditions, number of passengers, door status, and distance assessment between passengers. All these information are provided to the operator using visual analytics, but also via dedicated APIs, in order to automatically activate proper actions and mitigate undesirable behaviors and dangerous situations. An indicative example of people fighting is presented in Figure 2, where the abnormal activity notification is revealed, activating at the same time the mitigation protocol that has been allocated for these cases by the operator. A manual decision on these actions is also available, in case the supervising personnel considers that a different approach should be followed. Another case, where a graffiti painting activity along with a window attack are detected by the system, is illustrated in Figure 3.

An additional aspect of passenger safety is associated to the environmental safety within the vehicle. In this context, the service “Shuttle environment assessment” aims to maintain at acceptable levels the environmental conditions in the autonomous vehicle that may not be adequately controlled due to the absence of the shuttle driver. Minimum acceptable conditions and comfort, such as good air quality, acceptable odours and absence of smoke are necessary for the safe transport of the passengers, as well as the viability of the whole autonomous service, since lack of these conditions within the vehicle could significantly discourage potential passengers. Moreover, monitoring the environment conditions could enable for passengers’ alert and warning services via notifications, thus enhancing the user experience and safety during their trips. Thus, this service is considered essential for enhancing the engagement of the passengers to the new mobility infrastructure.

Figure 4: Overview of the AVENUE “shuttle environment assessment” service: A variety of environmental sensors is utilized to provide real-time measurements through the on-board PC to the AVENUE platform and the end-users (passengers, operators)

Under these circumstances, there are several instances that have to be considered in order for the prospective passengers to feel content and safe. In particular, while there would be no driver inside the vehicle, variable problems might come up. For example, there will be no presence of the operator staff inside the bus to prevent someone from lighting a cigarette. In addition, in quite high or low temperatures, there will be no driver in order to regulate the air conditioning system, or even if the air concentration of CO₂ inside the bus is high, and someone might get dizzy or exhibit breathing difficulties, there will be no driver so as to either open the windows or stop the shuttle, as well inform the operators and the competent authorities.

The buses should pose a comfortable environment for all the passengers and this feeling could undoubtedly be strengthened by controlling the temperature inside the vehicle. Besides, heating, ventilation and air conditioning control, now belong to the standard equipment on city buses. As a result, it is crucial for temperature sensors to be positioned in specific locations inside the vehicle. Simultaneously, these sensors will be connected with the air conditioning system and in cases that the temperature will exceed a suitable limit, the air condition will be put into operation. In that way, the existing temperature will be autonomously adjusted, in order to provide the appropriate indoor climate, namely not to be neither too hot nor too cold for the passengers.

In addition, detection of certain pollutants, such as CO₂, NO₂, or dust particles in the indoor environment, along with critical temperature variations, is important for the condition of certain passengers, especially ill people, such as asthma patients. Smoke in the vehicle, i.e. from a person that lights a cigarette, will deteriorate the passenger experience but may also put in danger the whole vehicle (danger of fire). These unfortunate cases may also result in significantly reducing the passenger engagement or even cancelling the autonomous transport service. In order to effectively address these unpleasant circumstances, the detection of certain events (air quality deterioration, smoke) may raise a notification or an alert to the supervisor

Figure 5: Detection of unaccompanied luggage. This service can operate as a utility for lost items as well as a domestic security control mechanism. A notification subsystem provides notification to the supervisor personnel.

and/or the suitable authorities (i.e. police, fire department) to take immediate action. This may be followed by appropriate notifications and/or instructions to the passengers on how to handle this situation, while the vehicle may also implement respective actions (i.e. regulate air conditioning system, stop in order the passengers to get off, drive to the closest fire department or move away from residential areas, etc.).

As depicted in Figure 4, the service is responsible for the timely, accurate, robust and automatic detection of any change in the air quality and the presence of smoke or fire, inside the vehicle. In case, there will be an alert on the system, notifications and instructions will be sent to the passengers and the operators and/or to the suitable authorities via the Avenue platform as well as the mobile app. Furthermore, detection of certain air quality indexes and pollutants in the indoor environment, along with critical temperature variations are necessary for providing a secure service to the passengers. In particular, a gas composition sensor could be used for checking the inside air quality. This sensor monitors the air intake of the heating, ventilation, and air conditioning system of the vehicle, while it detects undesirable gases and adjusts the system accordingly, by shutting off the intake and recirculating the indoor air back to the outside. Furthermore, humidity and temperature sensors could be used for measuring/regulating indoor air quality and adjusting the heating, ventilation, and air conditioning system settings accordingly. The designed system can be further extended by connecting other sensors, but also by applying AI-based analytics on the measured data to predict future situations and enhance environmental awareness within the vehicle. In this context, proper actions to equalize the environment to normal levels could be triggered automatically according to the output of the environmental prediction engine.

Figure 6: “Follow my kid” service capabilities: the identity of the enrolled passengers can be retrieved utilizing face recognition algorithms based on AI approaches. A notification subsystem provides notification to the “guardians” of the passengers.

3.2 Assistance Services

Another critical aspect within the autonomous public transportation system is associated to the assistance of the passengers, in various ways. Thus, several assistance services have been designed to facilitate adoption of the new mobility era. Among them, the “Unaccompanied luggage” service is capable of detecting items that are left into the vehicle, either they are forgotten, or they are placed on purpose. This service can operate as a utility for lost items as well as a domestic security control mechanism that enhances security aspects of the transportation system. An additional notification mechanism informs the supervisor personnel about each case and activates appropriate measures to handle the situation. An example of this service is illustrated in Figure 5, where a bag is left behind after the passenger has disembarked from the bus. The smart software detects the item and informs the operator. This service operates using the same cameras within the vehicle, simultaneously with the other services presented earlier.

In addition, the service “Follow my kid/grandparents” is designed to increase autonomy of non-fully autonomous people (Kids, Grandparent(s), disabled people etc.). It allows carers or family members to be sure that their beloved family members are safe while moving around the city using public transports. On the other hand, it will increase confidence to the non-fully autonomous people to use public transports knowing that their family can “be with them”. This service also utilizes surveillance sensors such as cameras, as well as smart software and hardware in the shuttle to maximize the feeling of security for the non-fully autonomous users.

Figure 7: “Follow my kid” service capabilities in the COVID-19 era: the identity of the enrolled passengers can be retrieved utilizing novel AI-based face recognition algorithms only from the upper part of the faces, since they are wearing a mask. A notification subsystem provides notification to the “guardians” of the passengers as well.

This service aims to address passengers’ fears regarding several possible instances that could arise in case there is no driver in the bus. Indicatively, the passengers feel discomfort travelling alone during nighttime, while parents are not able to know if their kids have reached their destination safely. Moreover, caregivers are not able to track passengers with dementia or other health issues. In order to address the aforementioned concerns on social and personal safety and security into the vehicle, certain measures need to be implemented. For example, third parties monitoring the route of minors or passengers with health issues could make their route much easier and less frightening. This may be followed by appropriate notifications and/or instructions to the third party, while the vehicle may also implement respective actions. Moreover, a solution for monitoring the routes of kids and patients supports safekeeping not only the users of the autonomous public shuttle but also the vehicle itself.

The service and application scenario proposes a full-fledged solution that allows designated “guardians” to follow the journeys of more vulnerable people, since the guardians can check the trip via a dashboard or mobile app, receive notifications via mobile app, add people to their “guarded” list, and share trips/position and estimated time arrival with others. A new passenger can be enrolled to the “Follow My Kid” service using a single image of his face which will be stored in a database. Using this as the reference image, the automated system will calculate the similarity for any new instance presented to it. Thus, the service can deduce in real-time the presence or not of a specific person into the vehicle, and provide appropriate notifications to the designated “guardians”. An indicative example is presented in Figure 6, where the identity of the passengers is retrieved via the installed cameras.

3.3 COVID-19 Enabled Services

The COVID-19 pandemic has created significant restrictions to passenger mobility through public transportation. With the rapid and continuous spreading to this day, COVID-19 is without doubt one of the main obstacles in the deployment of these services. New rules have been applied in public transportation, i.e. wearing a mask to decrease contamination within the vehicles, along with proximity rules between passengers. Therefore, the AVENUE services have been further modified to be adapted to the new reality formed by the COVID-19 pandemic. An indicative example is the “Follow my Kid” service, where novel AI based solutions have been created to allow recognition even for passengers wearing a mask, as depicted in Figure 7. In this way, the AI engine is adequately modified to allow for face recognition only from the upper part of the faces. The notification subsystem also provides notification to the “guardians” of the passengers as well. Further adaptations are elaborated to circumvent the implications that have been created by COVID-19.

4. Future Steps and Deployment Planning

The AVENUE project sites will continue operating until mid 2022, with plans to become permanent services and be expanded to cover larger areas and incorporate more mini-buses. The lessons that will be learned and data collected during this long deployment, will allow us to evaluate the acceptance of the services and understand the economic aspects and the regulatory and technological issues that need to be resolved for a large scale deployment.

The transport service quality and passengers safety and comfort, are the major preoccupation of the public transportation operators of the project. The automated AI-supported in-vehicle services aim to substitute the role of the safety driver and the essential functions he currently provides inside the shuttle. As a result, we are planning to experiment new services targeting the passenger comfort and safety and evaluate them under real operation conditions with a strong engagement of the passengers.

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